

Determination of Stability Constants of N-[2-Hydroxy-5-Methylbenzylidene]-4-Carboxyaniline Complexes with Y³⁺, La³⁺, Pr³⁺, Nd³⁺, Sm³⁺, Gd³⁺ and Dy³⁺

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IN the present communication the successive stability constants (log K₁ and log K₂) of the complexes of N-[2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzylidene]-4-carboxyaniline with various trivalent metal ions have been determined.

respectively. The protonation of the imino nitrogen probably does not take place as is observed from the titration curves.

The log K₁ and log K₂ values were calculated by least square method. The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of stability of metal chelates was found to be Y³⁺ > Sm³⁺ > Dy³⁺ > Nd³⁺ > Gd³⁺ > Pr³⁺ > La³⁺.

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TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES*

Cations	t = 25°					μ = 0.1 M			
	H ⁺	Y ³⁺	La ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Sm ³⁺	Gd ³⁺	Dy ³⁺	
log K ₁	10.75	9.49	7.95	8.23	8.29	8.90	8.28	8.57	
log K ₂	7.65	7.99	7.43	7.55	7.82	7.85	7.66	7.77	

*For proton association (H⁺) K₁ and K₂ correspond to the species LH and LH₂⁺ respectively while for metal ions, K₁ and K₂ correspond to the species LM and L₂M respectively.

Experimental

The ligand N-(2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzylidene)-4-carboxyaniline was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 5-methylsalicylaldehyde and *p*-aminobenzoic acid in methanol. The product was repeatedly crystallised to get an analytically pure compound (observed m.p. 258°).

All measurements were carried out at 25 ± 0.1°. The experimental details and computational methods were the same as described in earlier communications¹⁻⁴.

Results and Discussion

It may be stated here that the reagent does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by the rapid attainment of equilibrium and by the absence of any significant drift in pH meter readings even after one hour.

In the ligand it is the phenolic (OH) group which takes part in complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by the metal ion during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y', the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

The formation curve of $\bar{n}_A$ versus B extends over a range of 0.21 < $\bar{n}_A$ < 1.99 and is wave-like. From this curve pK^H , which corresponds to the association of proton to phenoxide ion of the reagent and pK^H_2 which corresponds to the association of proton to carboxylate ion of the reagent were obtained at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. These were further corroborated from the plots of

$$\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A} \right] \text{ vs } B \text{ and } \log \left[\frac{2 - \bar{n}_A}{\bar{n}_A - 1} \right] \text{ vs } B$$

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¹³C NMR Studies : Effect of Delocalization of Electrons on the Chemical Shift of Carbon Atoms in α -aryl- β -methyl cinnamonitriles*

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CNMR spectra of saturated and unsaturated nitriles are interesting for more than one reason. For example, the saturated nitriles show a remarkably small α -effect while the unsaturated nitrile such as the geometrical isomers of crotononitrile exhibit different chemical shift of α - and β -carbon atoms¹. A trisubstituted- α , β -unsaturated nitrile in which the delocalization of electrons is influenced by

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